

Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 1

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT





Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 3

A



B

Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT





Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 5

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 6

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 10

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 11

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 12

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 13

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 14

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 15

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 16

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 18

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 20

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 21

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 58

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 59

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 60

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 61

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B

Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 62

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B

Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 63

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B

Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NT



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Metric: NT



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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 68

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 69

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 70

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B

Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 71

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B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 72

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B

Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 73

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B

Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 74

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B

Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 75

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B

Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 76

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 77

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 81

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 86

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 87

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 88

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 89

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 90

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 91

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 92

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 94

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 95

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 96

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 97

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

ID: 98

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Source: theoretical-heterogeneous

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Metric: NT

